

INFLUENCE OF DYSBACTERIOSIS ON DYSPEPSIA IN TYPE 2 DIABETIC PATIENTS

*Katamadze N.,
Kandashvili T.,
Noniashvili M.*

Georgia. Tbilisi State Medical University

Abstract

The gastrointestinal tract is currently considered one of the large organs of the endocrine system. Although entero-endocrine cells make up only 1% of the total population of epithelial cells, unlike other cells, it produces more than 20 hormones. It was found that about 80% of the body's immune system is localized in the gastrointestinal tract. The ecosystem composition of the microbial community is dynamic and its composition depends on many factors. The intestinal barrier/permeability plays a critical role in the development of obesity and type 2 diabetes.

The aim of our study was to determine the influence of dysbacteriosis on dyspeptic manifestations in patients with type 2 diabetes. With results of your investigation we can conclude that the improvement of microflora in patients with type 2 diabetes and insulin resistance has a positive effect on dyspeptic manifestations. In particular, the long-term (12 weeks) inclusion of probiotics (*Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium breve*, *Bifidobacterium longum*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus lactis ssp. Lactis*, *Streptococcus thermophilus-20 X10⁹*), in a dose of 6 capsules per day, is important. It has a positive effect on gastro-intestinal complaints, as well as weight regulation.

Keywords: Obesity, Diabetes type 2, Gut microbiome, Probiotics.

The gastrointestinal tract is currently considered one of the large organs of the endocrine system. Although entero-endocrine cells make up only 1% of the total population of epithelial cells, unlike other cells, it produces more than 20 hormones [3]. By secreting intestinal peptides, which can act both locally, peripherally and centrally, entero-endocrine cells with the structural features of the intestinal mucosa can respond to changes in the intestinal environment.

It was found that about 80% of the body's immune system is localized in the gastrointestinal tract [2] which indicates the great importance of the intestine. The intestine offers a unique opportunity to regulate the immune response during the prevention or treatment of diseases originating in the said organ. Therefore, the endocrine activity of the gastrointestinal tract has long been an area of interest. The concept that the intestine also controls the activity of the pancreatic islets was supported by experiments showing that administration of intestinal extracts to animals reduced blood glucose levels.

The ecosystem composition of the microbial community is dynamic and its composition depends on many factors [13]. Recent experiments using animal models indicate that gut microflora is regulated by factors including genes, medications, and dietary intake. It is very important to take into account the fact that the intestinal microflora is easily changed by the influence of food.

The intestinal barrier/permeability plays a critical role in the development of obesity and type 2 diabetes [8]. The intestinal epithelium is a barrier, its main function is to limit the interaction of intestinal microflora, the local immune response and other parts of the body [10]. The integrity of the intestinal barrier maintains the function of the mucosa, which is very important in the formation of defense mechanisms. According to animal studies, lipopolysaccharides are also involved in the

regulation of processes related to diabetes mellitus, which are characterized by the enhancement of the inflammatory response.

The aim of our study was to determine the influence of dysbacteriosis on dyspeptic manifestations in patients with type 2 diabetes.

In order to assess the condition of the gastrointestinal tract, patients were surveyed with a questionnaire developed by us, which included simple questions (eg, do you suffer from diarrhea, constipation, flatulence, feeling full quickly, etc.) 132 patients aged 18 to 75 years were interviewed at the initial setup, including 87 women and 45 men. Out of 132 patients, 98 patients had type 2 diabetes. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were selected as first study group according to the level of glycated hemoglobin (glycated hemoglobin >6.5%) 12 patients were also selected to form the control group for first study group.

Also, taking into account the HOMA-index, the group with prediabetes/insulin resistance with 14 patients was formed - Second study group. For control group we choose 6 patients, who had insulin resistance.

Patients in both groups were treated with a set of probiotics, in which, based on the literature, the main role was assigned to the use of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*. We developed a set of the following composition: *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium breve*, *Bifidobacterium longum*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus lactis ssp. Lactis*, *Streptococcus thermophilus- 20 X10⁹*, which we gave to patients 2 caps. 3 times a day or 6 caps a day for 12 weeks.

Analyzing the results of the survey, it was found that out of 98 patients with type 2 diabetes, 76 patients had 3 or more gastro-intestinal complaints, namely flatulence - 72% of cases, constipation -16%, diarrhea - 12% -Picture N1

Picture N1 - Gastrointestinal complaints in patients with type 2 diabetes - results of a questionnaire

In the study group, the data obtained before and after the treatment were statistically processed according to the following indicators: diarrhea, constipation, flatulence, heartburn, feeling of nausea. As a result of the statistical research, it was obtained: diarrhea - decreased by 60%, in the control group it increased by 33%; Constipation - decreased by 73.5% in the study

group, unchanged in the control group, bloating - decreased by 73.9% in the study group, and decreased by 14.3% in the control group; heartburn - decreased by 60.7% in the study group, unchanged in the control group; Nausea - decreased by 64% in the study group, decreased by 33.3% in the control group;

We compared the complaints of the second study group and its control group. According to the results of the study: diarrhea in the second study group decreased by 71.4%, in its control group it increased by 50%; Constipation - second study group decreased by 57.1%, its control group did not change; Bloating - second

study group decreased by 57.1%, its control group decreased by 14.2%; Heartburn- in second study group decreased by 66.7%, in its control group it is unchanged; Nausea - decreased by 66.7% in second study group, increased by 50% in its control group;

Also, second study group, HOMA index, weight and waist circumference were determined before and after treatment. As a result of the statistical research, the following results were obtained: the average index of HOMA in the second study group decreased by 34.42%, and in its control group - by 1.32%, the average weight in the second study group decreased by 2.2%, and in its control group - by 1.36%; Waist circumference: second study group decreased by 4.3%, its control group increased by 1.4%.

After the inclusion of probiotics in the treatment of our study groups, in contrast to the control group where no probiotic treatment was performed, a reduction of some dyspeptic complaints was obtained, which in our opinion should be due to the correction of pronounced dysbacteriosis (confirmed by bacteriological examination of feces before treatment), which is also confirmed by literature data. As for the feeling of nausea, after the treatment, the condition of a certain number of patients improved from this point of view as well. As it is known, the feeling of nausea can be connected with the appearance of ketone bodies in the blood during hyperglycemia - ketosis. By regulating glycemia, this condition may be corrected. Treatment with probiotics had relatively little effect on reducing the feeling of heartburn, which is quite common and may be related to other anatomical features and pathologies of the esophagus and stomach.

We evaluated the change in HOMA index as a marker of insulin resistance before and after treatment with probiotics. In the study group, insulin resistance decreased by 34.42% on average. According to the literature insulin resistance decreases under the influence of probiotics, which is also confirmed by our work. The decrease in the index of insulin resistance is also confirmed by comparing the main and control groups, insulin resistance in the control group increased by 1.32%, which is probably related to the fact that we did not use probiotics in the control group.

The reduction in insulin resistance may be due to the following: Probiotics affect appetite and energy expenditure by producing acetate, propionate, and butyrate, which are short-chain fatty acids SCFA[1] The use of probiotics regulates the intestinal microbiota by increasing the number of Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus, which are responsible for the production of SCFA. It is believed that some probiotics can inhibit the absorption of dietary fat, increasing the amount of fat excreted in the stool[4] appetite regulating hormones are released. Probiotics may promote the release of appetite-suppressing hormones, namely glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and peptide YY (PYY)[10] Increased levels of these hormones cause the burning of calories and fat increase levels of fat-regulating proteins, which may lead to reduced fat storage[12]

There is a significant relationship between obesity and inflammation[6] By improving the intestinal mucosa, probiotics reduce the systemic inflammatory process, thereby reducing the risk of obesity. Inflammatory process is considered to be one of the genesis of obesity. Some Bifidobacterium spp. and Lactobacillus spp. Produces healthy conjugated linoleic acid (CLA). CLA also affects body weight by improving energy metabolism and lipolysis [7] In addition, probiotics increase the amount of Akkermansia muciniphila, which has a positive effect on the thickness of the mucosa and the integrity of the intestinal barrier. The beneficial effect is associated with a decrease in serum LPS levels and an improvement in the metabolic profile (decrease in plasma total cholesterol, LDL and TG levels and increase in HDL cholesterol). In addition, probiotics have a beneficial effect on populations of *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, which has an anti-inflammatory effect. On the other hand, probiotics produce bacteriocins and inorganic acids, which create an unfavorable environment for the growth of opportunistic pathogens and their metabolites, e.g. LPS and Indole. Increased intestinal permeability leads to increased plasma LPS levels

and increased expression of proinflammatory cytokines. Cytokines contribute to insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and increased visceral fat deposition. Taking probiotics strengthens/strengthens the intestinal barrier, increasing the production of tight junction proteins and mucins. Probiotics help reduce adipocyte size by reducing fatty acid uptake and increasing the expression of genes related to fatty acid oxidation. *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (LGG) inhibits fat accumulation in the liver by phosphorylating AMPK [5] *Lactobacillus* stimulates the production of certain cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), and therefore may be effective in regulating leptin gene expression [9] Leptin and adiponectin are potent anorexigenic hormones that inhibit food intake through receptors in the central nervous system [11]

The average weight in the second study group decreased by 2.2%, and in its control group - by 1.36%; It can be explained by the reduction of insulin resistance.

Therefore, we can conclude that the improvement of microflora in patients with type 2 diabetes and insulin resistance has a positive effect on dyspeptic manifestations. In particular, the long-term (12 weeks) inclusion of probiotics (*Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium breve*, *Bifidobacterium longum*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus lactis ssp. Lactis*, *Streptococcus thermophilus-20 X10⁹*), in a dose of 6 capsules per day, is important. It has a positive effect on gastro-intestinal complaints, as well as weight regulation.

References

1. A. Everard, P.D. Cani, Diabetes, obesity and gut microbiota, *Best Practice & Research Clinical Gastroenterology* 27 (2013) 73–83.
2. C.N. Lumeng, A.R. Saltiel, Inflammatory links between obesity and metabolic disease, *Journal of Clinical Investigation* 121 (2011) 2111–2117.
3. E. Naito, Y. Yoshida, K. Makino, et al., Beneficial effect of oral administration of *Lactobacillus casei* strain Shirota on insulin resistance in diet-induced obesity mice, *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 110 (2011) 650–657.
4. F. Calcinaro, S. Dionisi, M. Marinaro, et al., Oral probiotic administration induces interleukin-10 production and prevents spontaneous autoimmune diabetes in the non-obese diabetic mouse, *Diabetologia* 48 (2005) 1565–1575.
5. F.C. Hsieh, C.L. Lee, C.Y. Chai, et al., Oral administration of *Lactobacillus reuteri* GMNL-263 improves insulin resistance and ameliorates hepatic steatosis in high fructose-fed rats, *Nutrition & Metabolism* 10 (2013) 35
6. H. Panwar, H.M. Rashmi, V.K. Batish, et al., Probiotics as potential biotherapeutics in the management of type 2 diabetes – prospects and perspectives, *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews* 29 (2013) 103–112
7. H. Tilg, A. Kaser, Gut microbiome, obesity, and metabolic dysfunction, *Journal of Clinical Investigation* 121 (2011) 2126–2132.
8. J. Amar, C. Chabo, A. Waget, Intestinal mucosal adherence and translocation of commensal bacteria at the early onset of type 2 diabetes: molecular mechanisms
9. J. Qin, Y. Li, Z. Cai, et al., A metagenome-wide association study of gut microbiota in type 2 diabetes, *Nature* 490 (2012) 55–60.
10. Katamadze N. Kandashvili T. - „Gut Microbiota and Diabetes Mellitus“ *Cõrrahiyya*, 2019 №4
11. Katamadze N. Kandashvili T. “THE INFLUENCE OF MICROBIOTA ON METABOLIC DISORDERS”- *Cõrrahiyya*, 2020 № 2
12. Katamadze N. Kandashvili T. “The correlation between type 2 and gut microbiome” - *Znatsvena misel journal* N84, 2023
13. Shamanadze A., Tchokhnelidze I., Kandashvili T., Khutsishvili L. IMPACT OF MICROBIOME COMPOSITION ON QUALITY OF LIFE IN HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS